

THE GENERIC STRUCTURE POTENTIAL OF DOCTOR-PATIENT INTERACTION AT THE DIAGNOSTIC STAGE

Abstract

This study delves into the intricate dynamics of the diagnostic stage within doctor-patient interactions, aiming to propose a comprehensive framework that enhances the quality of healthcare communication. By examining over twenty-five recorded interactions from a state-owned medical centre in Nsukka, Enugu State, this research sheds light on the structural components and activities inherent in the diagnostic process.

Drawing upon Halliday and Hasan's (1985) Generic Structure Potential (GSP), the study identifies key elements within the diagnostic stage, including opening sequences (such as greetings and presentations of health issues) and information gathering (integrating and interpreting diagnostic information). Through meticulous analysis, a proposed structure emerges, encompassing the progression from initial interaction to treatment considerations.

Despite variations in the timing and sequence of information gathering, the study delineates a structured framework that encapsulates the essence of doctor-patient communication during the diagnostic phase. This framework offers insights into optimising communication strategies to meet patients' health needs effectively while facilitating informed decision-making by healthcare providers.

Furthermore, this research paves the way for future investigations into other stages of the doctor-patient interaction, contributing to the ongoing discourse on healthcare communication and medical practice. By extending the frontiers of research in the field of medicine, this study underscores the significance of linguistic analysis in understanding and enhancing healthcare delivery.

In conclusion, through rigorous examination and application of the GSP framework, this study elucidates the text structure of the diagnostic stage within doctor-patient interactions. By providing a systematic approach to analyzing communication patterns, it offers valuable insights into fostering meaningful dialogue and improving patient outcomes in healthcare settings.

Introduction

The dynamics of interactions between doctors and patients have become a focal point in healthcare studies. Over the past two decades, both descriptive and experimental research have sought to illuminate the communication process during medical consultations. Scholars such as Coulthard and Ashby (1976), Labov and Fanshel (1977), Coleman and Burton (1985), van Naerssen (1985), Myerscough (1992), Wodak (1997), Chimombo and Roseberry (1998), and Valero-Garces (2002) have examined medical communication from the perspectives of discourse and conversation analysis.

In Nigeria, studies on medical communication, such as Adegbite's (1991) examination of herbalist-client interactions in Yoruba and Ogunbode's (1994) and Oloruntoba-Oju's (1995) descriptions of medical professional communication needs, are relatively scarce. However, the insights gained from these studies remain limited, likely due to the inherent complexity of the doctor-patient relationship. This relationship involves interactions between individuals occupying non-equal positions, often occurs involuntarily, addresses issues of vital importance, carries emotional weight, and necessitates close cooperation.

Within medical encounter research, language interaction serves as a focal point. Scholars like Frankel (2000) and other medical interview experts (Bird and Cohen-Cole 1990; Cohen-Cole 1991; Lazare, Putnam, and Lipkin 1995) have identified three elements of the doctor-patient contact: the interview (or diagnosis), treatment, and follow-up. They assert that each of these tasks possesses its own structure and distinguishing characteristics, which can be analyzed independently or as part of a larger discourse.

The first task, data collection, aims to establish a diagnosis, propose treatment, and predict the course of sickness. The second task involves relationship building, creating a safe space for patients to convey diagnostic information and express their experiences, while also addressing physical and emotional stress and negotiating treatment plans. Finally, the third task entails sharing diagnostic findings (whether positive, negative, or inconclusive) and educating patients about their conditions and treatment options.

In this study, we will focus specifically on the diagnostic aspect of the first task, which possesses its own structure and characteristics within the interview process. This aspect exploits the concept of the "interaction order," as proposed by Goffman (1983), and will be central to our analysis.

2. The Diagnostic Stage: Understanding Patient-Doctor Dynamics

In the realm of medical diagnosis, the process of understanding a patient's ailment is akin to studying a biographical narrative marred by pathology. Balint (1964) encapsulates this by noting that individuals often seek medical consultation either when their ailment has manifested into a full-blown illness or even before its onset. This stage garners significant attention across sociological, psychological, anthropological, and linguistic literature, where diagnosis is defined as "the process of determining the nature of a disorder by considering the patient's signs and symptoms, medical background, and – where necessary – results of laboratory tests and X-ray examinations" (Martin, 2000).

Patients, driven by a belief in the authority and expertise of medical practitioners, place their trust in doctors to address their health concerns. Within the therapy session, doctors wield a considerable degree of power, structuring and managing the interaction (Mondada, 1998), often assuming a position of superiority over their patients, a dynamic that may or may not be embraced by the latter (Leonardi & Viaro, 1983).

The diagnostic procedure unfolds as follows: a patient experiences a health issue and becomes the first to recognize and contemplate their symptoms, possibly deciding to seek medical assistance (Sarter, 2014). This initiates an iterative process wherein information is systematically gathered, integrated, interpreted, and ultimately leads to a working diagnosis. Techniques such as conducting clinical history and interviews, physical examinations, diagnostic tests, and consultations with other practitioners are employed to collect pertinent information necessary for understanding the patient's health concern. Importantly, these

methods can be applied at various junctures, and diagnostic information can be obtained through diverse sequences (Parasuraman et al., 2000).

Studies on doctor-patient diagnostic interactions

Studies examining doctor-patient diagnostic interactions have garnered significant attention within linguistics and related disciplines. These investigations often encompass a wide array of diagnostic encounters, ranging from history-taking to examinations and medical tests. Notable contributions by scholars such as Maynard (1991a, 1991b, 1991c, 1992, 2003, 2004) and Peräkylä (1998) have focused specifically on diagnostic news delivery systems, shedding light on the intricacies of this crucial aspect. Odebunmi (2006) provides insights derived solely from doctors' oral discourses on diagnosis, elucidating locutions intended for patient comprehension. Furthermore, Odebunmi (2013) underscores the significance of greetings and courtesy within medical speech, highlighting the presence of institutional and cultural alignments. Faleke (2005) delves into the pragmatic dimensions of nurse-patient interactions, while Salami (2006) analyzes interactions between doctors and pregnant women. Ogunbode (1992), Alabi (1996), and Oloruntoba-Oju (1996) have explored various facets of medical communication. In their examination of discourse tact in doctor-patient interactions in South Western Nigeria, Adegbite and Odebunmi (2006) propose a framework wherein the doctor elicits information and provides direction, while the patient reciprocates with insights to aid in diagnosing medical challenges and needs. This body of research offers valuable insights into the nuanced roles and dynamics inherent in doctor-patient diagnostic interactions, enriching our understanding of this complex discourse domain.

4. The organisation of Medical interviews in preparation for the Diagnostic Stage

In Nigerian hospitals, clients can go to any hospital at whatever time of day they believe they will be able to access the medical personnel for medical assistance since making an appointment with a doctor in advance is not mandatory. They are assigned doctors to whom their case notes are submitted after showing duplicates of their registration documents or giving their registration numbers to hospital records officers. Clients are required to wait on a comfortable seat outside the doctors' offices for their turn. When it's a client's turn, he or she

is summoned by name (a complete name without a title). He or she is normally sitting on the left side of the doctor's table, and the consultation spans between 5 and 20 minutes, during which the diagnostic enquiries take place in the medical interview.

Studies on Generic Structure Potential

Studies on Generic Structure Potential (GSP) have been extensively explored by scholars such as Halliday and Hassan (1989), Olagunju (2015), and Teo (1996), shedding light on the intricate structure of various text types.

According to Halliday and Hassan (1989), the examination of optional and obligatory elements, along with their structural arrangement, allows for a comprehensive understanding of the text structure across different genres. Their study delved into the service encounter of a shop transaction, identifying macro elements such as Greeting (G), Sale Initiation (SI), Sale Enquiry (SE), Sale Request (SR), Sale Compliance (SC), Sale (S), Purchase (P), Purchase Closure (PC), and Finis (F). These elements were observed to follow a specific sequence (G). (SI) ^ [(SE). { SR^ SC^ } ^S^] P^ PC (^F).

Similarly, Olagunju (2015) examined the generic structure potential of football match reports in newspapers. Analyzing 36 randomly selected reports from Nigerian newspapers, the study identified obligatory elements including Title (T), Preamble (P), Online thesis (OT), and Online thesis Expatiation (OTE), along with optional features such as Voice insertion, Offline thesis insertion, Offline thesis Expatiation, Evaluation, Prediction, and Winding up. The structure was structured as [T]^ [P]^ [OT]^ [OTE]^ {VI} {OTI} {(OFTE)}^ (Eva)^(Pre)^(WUp).

Teo (1996) investigated the GSP structure of modern songs through an analysis of twelve songs by Bruce Springsteen, categorised into Narrative songs and Non-Narrative Songs. The study revealed that narrative songs followed a frame of [<(Abstract)>] ‘Orientation’)^ Crisis^^ (Coda), while non-narrative songs adopted a structure of <(Abstract)>^Crisis ‘()’.

These studies highlight the presence of obligatory, reversible, and optional elements within the frames of various text types, providing valuable insights into the structure and organisation of different genres.

6. Theoretical Framework

The Generic Structure Potential model (henceforth, GSP) established by Michael Halliday and Ruqiyah Hasan (cf. Halliday/Hasan 1985 and Hasan, 1996) provides theoretical insights for this research. Contextual Configuration (CC) — a specific set of values that realises the field, tenor, and mode—"allows claims about the texts structures" to be made, according to the model (Halliday & Hasan, 1985, p. 56). Contextual Configuration is important for textural unity and for revealing the relationship between a text and its surroundings. A CC can, for example, anticipate the following about text structure:

1. Obligatory elements - What elements must be present?
2. Optional elements – What elements are possible to appear?
3. Element sequencing - Which arrangements of elements are required and which are optional?
4. Iteration - How often should certain elements appear?

According to Halliday & Hasan (1985), given a specific CC, we can represent the whole range of optional and necessary elements, as well as their sequence, in such a way that we exhaust the possibilities. Every text has the potential to have a text structure that is ideal for a specific CC. This possibility is referred to as the genre's structural potential or its generic structural potential (GSP). GSP captures the qualities of texts that correspond to a specific genre. It denotes the ideal textual organisation for writings within a genre, which is determined by the genre's social/communicative goals. It's a powerful tool that allows for a wide range of conceivable structures to be realised. According to Halliday and Hasan (1985), a certain GSP is essentially and sufficiently realised by a collection of mandatory elements. Therefore, we can summarise the propositions of the Hassan theory of generic structure potentials as follows:

- a. Features of contextual configuration could be used for making some kind of prediction about text structure and the sequence and order of the elements in the structure. Contextual configuration is composed of three components: Field of discourse, tenor of discourse, and mode of discourse, and the thought of it as a variable that is represented by some specific values.
- b. Every genre has a generic structure potential, which includes three kinds of elements: Obligatory, optional, and recursive. The generic structure potential for a genre is a linear combination of the elements in a order of sequence.
- c. Genre is defined by obligatory elements in structure. Consequently, the obligatory elements and their sequence define the genre to which the text belongs, and the function of the optional elements may account for the variation in all the texts that belong to the same genre. (adapted from Ren, 2010, p. 233)

7. Data and method

A total of fifty doctor-patient interactions were recorded at a state-owned medical centre in Nsukka, Enugu State. Consent was obtained from the hospital management to conduct the recordings and take notes during the interactions.

From the recorded interactions, twenty-five were selected for analysis based on their relevance to the study's objectives. These selections were purposefully made to ensure a representative sample that captured the spectrum of interactions during the diagnostic stage.

The analysis of the collected data was conducted using Halliday and Hasan's (1985) Generic Structure Potential (GSP) framework. This framework provided a systematic approach for identifying and analyzing the structural elements and linguistic features characteristic of the diagnostic stage in doctor-patient interactions.

Through the application of the GSP framework, the researcher systematically examined the recorded interactions to identify patterns and structures inherent in the communication

process. The analysis focused on capturing the qualities of texts specific to the diagnostic stage, enabling a detailed exploration of the linguistic dynamics involved.

Overall, the methodology employed a combination of recording, selection, and analysis techniques to investigate the diagnostic stage of doctor-patient interactions. By leveraging the GSP framework, the study aimed to provide insights into the structural organisation and linguistic features of these interactions, contributing to our understanding of communication in healthcare settings.

8. Data Analysis

The impact of diagnosis on patient treatment, research, and policy is significant. Diagnosis is both a method and a classification scheme, or a "pre-existing set of classifications agreed upon by the medical profession to define a specific ailment," according to (Jutel, 2009). Because clinical decision making will be tailored to a correct understanding of the patient's health problem when a diagnosis is accurate and made in a timely way, a patient has the best chance for a positive health outcome (Holmboe and Durning, 2014). We can interpret patients' speech as guided by their desire to be properly diagnosed and treated for diseases, and physicians' speech as guided by their desire to properly diagnose and treat diseases using the accurate interactional order and paradigm. It is very clear that doctor-patient interaction at the diagnostic stage has a structure. The interactional order Goffman (1983) is well organized and laden with component activities. These activities often begin with the opening sequence; the next is the problem presentation, history taking, physical examination, diagnosis, treatment recommendation and the closing sequence (Robinson, 2003; Brye & Long, 1976; Heritage & Maynard, 2006)

The following instances are interactions between an Optician and a patient at the diagnostic stage:

Data 1

The following is how the diagnostic procedure works

00 Pat: Good morning, Doc,

01 Opt: (doctor calls patient in) Welcome, Good morning. Mama, can you explain what is wrong with your eye?

- 02 Pat: My eyes drips water and causes me headache whenever I blink or close it.
- 03 Opt: When did you start noticing this?
- 04 Pat: One year ago
- 05 Opt: Where is your face mask?
- 06 Pat: We do not have.
- 07 Opt: You will need to get one before I can run an eye test for you.
- (Patient goes to get the mask as instructed while the doctor attends to a follow-up patient in the interim)
- 08 Pat: I am back sir.
- 09 Opt: Mama, you are back. Okay sit down and face this side. Look straight at the mirror, don't look at me. Let me know the cause of the constant water drippings from the eye. (The optician looks into the eyes) Close one of your eyes with your palm and open the other. Can you see me? What can you see? Can you see what is written? (chuckles)
- 10 Pat: No
- (Eye test continues)
- 11 Opt: From what I can see, Mama you have cataract and it is at the matured stage. You have to be patient. Therefore, I will be referring you to a private hospital (in an eye specialist hospital) for an operation because we have not started to perform eye operation in this hospital.

Data 2

- 12 Opt: Have been here before?
- 13 Pat: I was here last two days Dr. C didn't have light to check my eyes that day and I needed her to check them. The last reading glasses she gave me spoilt so I came for it and there was no light had to go back home because I came from Kogi. My husband works here

- 14 Opt: ok, you are coming from Kogi. Why is that you did not check it at Kogi state?
- 15 Pat: Ehen... My husband is here now so I came from there and I decided to check it and I came here to spend the weekend. Sir, I bought an eye glass, the one they sell along the roadside. Please I want to ask if it will have an adverse effect on me.
- 16 Opt: What do you think?
- 17 Pat: I don't know I am not an eye doctor.
- 18 Opt: You don't need to be an eye doctor before you know that. As somebody that is literate, what do you think? At least you went to school?
- 19 Pat: It's just a reading glass now as long as I can read with it; I think I am okay with it. But you being a medical doctor can give me the right advice on what is the right.
- 20 Opt: So if you need surgery, do you go to the market and buy surgery?
- 21 Pat: No!
- 22 Opt: That's the way I can answer your question. If somebody needs surgery or a person wants to deliver a baby does the person do that in the market?
- 23 Pat: Some even deliver on the road so you can't compare delivery with this one (chukeles)
- 24 Opt: Even those that deliver on the road, is it the right thing?
- 25 Pat: It is an emergency now!
- 26 Opt: Its emergency because of negligence. Do you understand it? They were careless about it that is why they deliver on the road. Because if you are someone that has been going for your antenatal and you have been seeing your doctor, you doc would tell you. But now, you are not going for antenatal and you are not seeing a doctor, therefore you delivering in the market. So ...
- 27 Pat: (chukeles)
- 28 Opt: You know in Nigeria what people do and before you know it becomes a normal thing, like buying this thing in the market, now it has become a normal thing but it's not the right thing to do. Now we are going to test you. The right thing to do

is that you get tested before a glasses can be issued to you, you do not just go and buy glasses from the market.

- 29 Pat: But what of this popularly known eye treatment group in town?
- 30 Opt: They employ doctors, and they are a private group who decided to start up an eye clinic.
- 31 Opt: Okay, take this note to the director's office; you will pay #1000 for test for glasses and you will come back with the receipt.
- 32 Pat: Okay that way?
- 33 Opt: No! Director's office is this way down the lane
- 34 Pat: But I thought it should be covered under NHIS?
- 35 Opt: Madam everything is not under NHIS? I know that is why you left Kogi state; you are here telling me that you came to see your husband
- 36 Pat: (laughs ...) ehen Yes now! We have the NHIS here so it's an opportunity for me
- 37 Opt: I know I know...

The data above divides the diagnostic structure of the doctor-patient interaction into two stages, which are;

- 1) Opening sequences
- 2) Information Gathering
- 3) Proceeding to the Treatment stage.

Opening sequence

From the data above, it is obvious that the structure of a doctor - patient interaction at the diagnostic stage first begins with the opening which include **greeting** (optional) as in 00 and 01 in the first data, where that doctor may or may not respond depending on the available contextual factors.

Excerpt 1

00 Pat: Good morning Doc,

01 Opt: (doctor calls patient in) Welcome, Good morning. Mama

In the Nigerian hospital, interactions are typically clinical, driven by the Westernization of doctors' education. The meetings' interactional substance is significantly reduced, with a focus on transactional discussion (cf. Adebite, 1991; Odebunmi, 2006), hence greetings occurs more as an optional element than obligatory in the opening sequence.

The next to this is the **presentation of health issue**. This starts with a **broad enquiry** from the doctor that opens the avenue for the patient to give an account of what symptom the patient have been going through. Such as;

Excerpt 2

01 Opt: ...can you explain what is wrong with your eyes? (Data 1)

12 Opt: Have been here before? (Data 2)

It occurs when a patient who had thought intensely about his symptoms is given an opportunity to speak with the doctor in order to seek medical help. It involves a strategy to direct or redirect the patient to the main focus of the interactional transaction.

Information Gathering

This involves an iterative or repeatable process of gathering information, integrating information, interpreting that information, and determining a working diagnosis. The doctor primarily engages the patient in series of further questions that may be useful in identifying a patient's health problem.

Excerpt 3

01 Opt: Have been here before?

02 Pat: My eyes drips water and causes me headache whenever I blink or close it

03 Opt: When did you start noticing this?

04 Pat: One year ago

05

06 Pat: I was here last two days Dr. C didn't have light to check my eyes that day and I needed her to check them. The last reading glasses she gave me spoilt so I came for it and there was no light had to go back home because I came from Kogi. My husband works here.

Other activities that is embedded in this stage involves taking of patient's medical history, giving of physical exam, performing diagnostic tests, and referring or consulting with other practitioners of identifying a patient's health problem. At times a patients' medical history is already documented in the patients' medical record or file while the physical examination can be drawn from the data provided above;

Excerpt 4

09 Opt: Mama, you are back. Okay sit down and face this side. Look straight at the mirror, don't look at me. Let me know the cause of the constant water drippings from the eye. (The optician looks into the eyes) Close one of your eyes with your palm and open the other. Can you see me? What can you see? Can you see what is written?
(chuckles)

10 Pat: No

(Eye test continues)

A list of possible diagnoses also called a **differential diagnosis** can be made from the combination of the above (taking of patient's medical history, giving of physical exam, performing diagnostic tests, and referring or consulting with other practitioners of identifying a patient's health problem), or a **working diagnosis** (that particular single prospective diagnosis that a doctor may decide to work with.). The above data provided the doctor with a single working diagnosis that the doctor worked with and that was cataract. The series of possible interviews and interrogations as well as physical examination that was engaged in by the doctor eventually produced a working diagnosis that lead to the referral of that patient to a private hospital.

Excerpt 5

11 Opt: From what I can see, Mama you have cataract and it is at the matured stage. You have to be patient. Therefore, I will be referring you to a private hospital (in an eye

specialist hospital) for an operation because we have not started to perform eye operation in this hospital.

It could also happen that doctors may evaluate multiple diagnostic hypotheses as reasons for a patient's symptoms, and this list will be modified as more evidences is obtained during the diagnostic process. This is a process known as diagnostic modification and refinement (Kassirer et al., 2010). Patients are supposed to be informed of the working diagnosis, which involves a degree of explanations for the signs and symptoms that is coherent with the patient's context (physiology, risk factors).

Moving to the Treatment Stage

Once a specific condition has been identified through either a differential or a working diagnosis, and the patient's particular ailment has been determined, doctors progress to recommending treatment—a pivotal juncture in the interaction (Jutel, 2009). It's worth noting that doctors don't always require diagnostic certainty before initiating treatment. Instead, the aim of gathering information during the diagnostic process is to reduce ambiguity enough to make the most informed treatment decisions possible (Kassirer, 1989). Furthermore, treatment itself can play a role in refining and informing a working diagnosis, creating a feedback loop that informs the information-gathering stage of the diagnostic process (Kassirer et al., 2010).

The general structure of doctor-patient interaction during the diagnostic stage can be outlined as follows:

1. Greeting and Broad Enquiry (BE)
2. Gathering Information (GI) including patient's medical history (PMH), physical examination (PE), performing diagnostic tests (PDT), and consulting with other practitioners to identify the patient's health problem (COP)
3. Integrating Information (I) and Interpretation (Int I)
4. Working Diagnosis (WD)
5. Proceeding to the Treatment Stage (PTS)

Therefore, the sequence can be represented as follows: [Greeting (G) ^ Broad Enquiry (BE)] ^ {Gathering Information (GI) <Patient's Medical History (PMH)> <Physical Exam (PE)> <Diagnostic Tests (PDT)> <Consulting with Other Practitioners (COP)>} ^ {Integrating Information (I) {Interpretation (Int I)}} ^ [Working Diagnosis (WD)] ^ [Proceeding to the Treatment Stage (PTS)].

Conclusion

This study has presented the components activities in that occur in the diagnostic stage of the doctor-patient interaction. It proposes a working generic structure potential for the sake of satisfying the health needs of patients as well as to enhancing a more qualitative response from the doctors to their patients. Although the information-gathering involved in the diagnosis stage can be employed at different times, and diagnostic information can be obtained in different order (Kassirer et al., 2010), we can still propose a possible structure for the doctor-patient interaction at diagnostic stage as comprising of: Opening Sequences catalogue (greetings, presentation of health issue), Information Gathering (, integrating information, interpreting that information, and determining a working diagnosis) and the Proceeding to treatment stage. This can be catalogued as; [**G**> ^ **BE**]. ^ {**GI** < **PMH**> < **PE**> < **PDT**>. < **COP** >} ^ {**Ing** { **I** { **Int I** } .^ [**WD**>} ^ [**PTS**].

This study gives room for further researches on other stages of the doctor patient interaction to be done. It also promotes and extends the frontiers of research in the field of medicine.